

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Community Cluster

Semantic Modelling & Linked Open Data

Chairs: Florian Thiery (LEIZA); Karsten Tolle (Uni Frankfurt)

SC Decision: 28.04.2023

Bodies Involved: TA1-6 plus div. Participants

External Linking: NFDI4Culture (TA2); NFDI4Memory (TA1, TA2); NFDI4Earth (SIG); NFDI4Ing (SIG); CAA International / -DE; Pelagios Network; DHd AG Graphen und Netzwerke; RDA DE e.V.; CIDOC Gruppe; FG Dokumentation Deutscher Museumsbund; Wikimedia Deutschland e.V.; FAIR Digital Objects Forum; AG Objekte.Digitalität.Hochschulen

Subject & Objective

The Community Cluster focuses on the following topics: Semantic modelling and Linked Open Data, fuzziness and wobbliness, structured data in the "Wikimedia Universe" (especially Wikidata), as well as ontologies and reference models (e.g. CIDOC CRM, EDM). The CC also deals with mapping ontologies and standards for uncertainties and ambiguities.

This Community Cluster covers the parts of the research data lifecycle relating to processing, enrichment and publication. The central topic of this cluster is the interdisciplinary exchange of knowledge in the field of interoperable knowledge modelling of object and collection-related data with the help of semantics to enable FAIR data, especially regarding its traceability and reuse.

Out of Scope

The Community Cluster does not deal with the content-related processing of standardised data (e.g. provenance research; restoration) and subject-specific thesauri. The cluster also does not deal with the modelling of database structures for collection management (e.g. easydb, MuseumPlus, robotron*Daphne, CollectiveAccess, etc.).

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Intended Work Results

The following work results are aimed at TWGs:

- Development of community standards for interoperable semantic modelling of objects and processes
- Mapping of ontologies (e.g. CIDOC CRM, EDM, nomisma.org, authority files & community-driven vocabularies)
- Development of community standards on fuzziness and wobbliness (e.g. uncertainty, vagueness, accuracy and precision)
- Whitepaper: "How to create LOD?"
- Whitepaper: "How to integrate Data in Wikidata?"
- Development of workflows and data models for Wikidata projects and Wikidata properties